

LARGE-SCALE TESTS OF THE SPHERE RECONSTRUCTION PROGRAMS

Status report 1987 Dec 16

Simulations

Abscissa files are produced on tapes in the format specified by Petersen (1987 March 18). From LOS23-06 onwards, a checksum is however written in the first four bytes of every block (thus overwriting 'NDAC' in the file label). Furthermore, 3200 bpi density is used for these tests in order to simplify tape handling (one year per tape).

LOS23-03 (generated Nov 26): 0.5 year (411 sets, 114,488 stars, 807,436 abscissae) with perfect and noisy data (stored respectively as 'smoothed' and 'geometric' solutions). For the noisy data we have

$$\sigma_{\text{absc}} = 3 \text{ to } 7 \text{ mas (depending on magnitude etc)}$$

$$\sigma_{\text{zpt}} = 10 \text{ mas}$$

$$\sigma_{\text{slit}} = 0 \quad (\text{no slit errors})$$

$$\sigma_{\text{mult}} = 0 \quad (\text{no additional noise for double or multiple stars})$$

LOS23-06 (generated Dec 11): 1.0 year (822 sets, 114,488 stars, 1,607,237 abscissae) with noisy data with and without slit errors ($\sigma_{\text{slit}} = 1.2''$ and 0, respectively). Noise levels otherwise as above. This simulation includes also a global distortion of the abscissae according to the formula

$$\Delta a = (0.1 \text{ mas}) \sin 3\psi + (0.04 \text{ mas}) \cos 6\psi$$

where ψ is the mean abscissa of the sun in the set.

Results from running SORT23, ACCU23, SOLV23:

Run# 301 (0.5 year, perfect data)

The solution included two astrometric parameters per star (α , δ), one zero point per set, and four global parameters (sine and cosine for ψ and 2ψ). Sorting the observations (SORT23) took 3.1 h (real time) including tape I/O operations. Setting up the normals and updating the positions (ACCU23) took 5.9 h, while the Cholesky reduction/solution (SOLV23) took 0.5 h.

The rms position update was $7.6 \cdot 10^{-7}$ mas (maximum update $9.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mas). The rms zero point update was $1.2 \cdot 10^{-7}$ mas and the absolutely largest global parameter $4.0 \cdot 10^{-9}$ mas.

Run# 302 (0.5 year, noisy data) and 303 (2nd pass)

The unknowns were the same as in run# 301 and the executing times were about the same.

The rms position updates were 8.1 mas (α) and 6.0 mas (δ), the rms zero point update 9.90 mas and the maximum global parameter 0.0096 mas ($= 0.90\sigma$). The formal s.d. of the RGC zero points was about 0.1 mas.

The RGC zero points and the positional errors were analyzed for a global misorientation of the reference system. Separate least-squares solutions were made from the RGC zero points and from each of the position components. Result:

solution based on	<i>x-orient.</i>	<i>y-orient.</i>	<i>z-orient.</i>
RGC zero points	+0.030	-0.106	+0.473 mas
$\Delta\alpha \cos \delta$	+0.017	-0.105	+0.473 mas
$\Delta\delta$	+0.029	-0.116	(undefined)
$\Delta\alpha \cos \delta + \Delta\delta$	+0.026	-0.113	+0.475 mas

The solution for the global orientation was highly significant, *e.g.* the χ^2 for zero point errors was reduced from 2656 before solution to 560 after solution (408 d.o.f.). The χ^2 for the solution combining $\Delta\alpha \cos \delta$ and $\Delta\delta$ was, after adjustment, 228,096 (227,223 d.o.f.). The conclusion from these tests is that the solution is globally consistent to the order of 0.01 mas.

Run# 401 (1.0 year, noisy data but without slit errors) and 402 (2nd pass)

This solution included three parameters per star (α , δ , π), one zero point per set, and eight global parameters (sine and cosine for ψ , 2ψ , 3ψ , and 6ψ). Result for the global parameters:

$$s1 = -0.0373 \text{ mas} \pm 0.5056 \text{ mas} \quad (\text{indeterminate due to parallaxes})$$

$$c1 = +0.0011 \text{ mas} \pm 0.0069 \text{ mas}$$

$$s2 = +0.0003 \text{ mas} \pm 0.0049 \text{ mas}$$

$$c2 = +0.0026 \text{ mas} \pm 0.0053 \text{ mas}$$

$$s3 = +0.1011 \text{ mas} \pm 0.0049 \text{ mas} \quad (\text{should be } 0.1000 \text{ mas})$$

$$c3 = +0.0054 \text{ mas} \pm 0.0057 \text{ mas}$$

$$s6 = -0.0008 \text{ mas} \pm 0.0053 \text{ mas}$$

$$c6 = +0.0290 \text{ mas} \pm 0.0053 \text{ mas} \quad (\text{should be } 0.0400 \text{ mas})$$

For position and parallax errors, see histograms.

LC523-03

Run #302

Run # 303

